

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE SOCIALIZATION OF THE INDIVIDUAL

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Annotation: *A person is a member of a particular society, as a member of society he is in a different system of relations. A person cannot exist outside of society, without his influence. Therefore, the issues of the interdependence of the individual and society are important, topical issues. The set of people in a society depends on the nature of the interactions that occur between these people, the content of the complex social partnership activities they carry out. As long as everyone lives in a society, he strives to have a special place and an independent position in it. He exemplifies aspiration, talent and activism.*

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The product of interpersonal-social and interpersonal relations is the individual, who is the subject of conscious activity. The most important of the qualities pertaining to a person is that he perceives these external, social influences with his consciousness and perception (object) and then acts as a subject of these influences. A person's social behavior is influenced by various external forces, a set of social relations: political, ideological, economic, spiritual, moral and others. The individual is influenced by different systems of social relations, and many social institutions are associated with the family, neighborhood, art, culture, etc. These

influences essentially determine certain specific areas of interaction between individuals who are actually members of society.

[1.As a member of society, various relationships are influenced, first of all, in the sphere of relations arising in the process of production and consumption of material wealth. The psychology of the individual depends on whether his freedom is oppressive, whether he has political rights, whether he discusses social issues, or whether he is an executor of the will of the ruling class. The person is also under the influence of ideological relationships. The system of ideas about society shapes the psychology of the individual, his worldview, social institutions. The main reason why a person is called a product of social relations is that he is always in the circle of people, in the sphere of interaction that they know. This indicates that one of the most leading and influential activities of an individual is communication. In the process of communication, people interact with each other. And as a result, from the point of view of society, people, personal qualities, psychology is established in the establishment and in other relations in general. The wider a person's sphere of communication, the more diverse his connection with different spheres of life, and the deeper a person can penetrate the world of social relations, the richer his spiritual world will be.] A person's position is a system of his or her relationships. The mental characteristics of a person determine a person's social experience, his social institutions.

The process of a person's development should not be seen as the development of the emotional and volitional cognitive processes that characterize a person's individuality. A person develops in a group, that is, under the influence of interactions and communication established in that group. Hence, group development is manifested as a factor in the development of the individual in the group. An individual's specific need, that is, individual characteristics, satisfies the need to be a person and allows him to perform various tasks. Group communities with this level of development are of great importance.

[2.The development of the individual can be thought of as joining a new social environment and uniting with it. The stability of this environment can vary.

Conditionally, this environment is assumed to be constantly evolving (e.g., first grade of school, production crew, each part, etc.) In a relatively stable environment, a person's development goes through 3 stages. These are the stages of adaptation, individualization and integration. Individuality - the distinctive social characteristics and psyche of the individual and its irreversibility. Adaptation - as a result of adaptation of the sensory organs to the driving force, a certain sensitivity may increase or decrease. Sensitivity to strong influences to weak influences gradually increases. As the effect increases, the sensitivity gradually decreases. Integration - a concept that describes the state of interdependence of individual parts and functions of the body and the process that leads to such a state.] The process of development of the person should not be considered as the development of emotional and volitional cognitive processes characterizing the individuality of the person. A person develops in a group, that is, under the influence of interactions and communication established in that group. Man is active by nature. The structure of human activity includes a variety of involuntary, automated characters (facial expressions, pantomime, gestures, etc.), as well as imaginary movements with a high degree of complexity. It is said that it is a known habit to perform actions that are necessary for a person to perform under certain conditions. Even the most ephemeral portrait cannot give a complete picture of a person's character from his usual actions and movements. When a character affects a person's appearance, he finds a free expression in his actions, behavior, and activities. Character is first of all freely expressed in people's actions, attitudes and activities. Character is first of all freely expressed in people's behavior, attitudes and activities. Character must first be judged on the basis of human behavior. Their essence is more fully reflected in these actions.

[3.The spiritual world of man is made up of a continuous set of actions, one directly requiring the other, and they rule in a system of continuous chains. In the same way the person is in the psyche impressions of the external environment, memories of the past, creative thoughts about the future, good intentions, desires, goals and aspirations, reflections, thoughts and problems, emotional experiences,

volitional qualities are constantly intertwined. In exchange for rin replacement, a solid foundation is laid for the ontogenetic world.]

The course of the spiritual world, its speed, content, form, scope, feature, character, the quality, the mechanism is different, it is observed in each person in different ways. This is probably why people respond differently to natural phenomena, social life events, factors, and influences. while creating an emotional environment that encourages the maturity of each individual and the high work capacity of the whole team, it is important to start by regulating the relationships between group members and the values that prevail in them. Your relationship with the teaching staff is formal and informal structures are highlighted. Here, both structures are considered only from the point of view of the individual in the community. The formal structure of a relationship is a system of situations (positions) given by society from the outside that the community must function. In the system of informal interpersonal relationships, the circumstances are determined by the uniqueness of each student and the characteristics of that class. Even in elementary school, your child should be in a certain, engaging position in the classroom, such as a leader, the best student, the best athlete, and so on. aspiration is observed. Social status is a two-dimensional measure: an individual's social behavior and characterized by the social hope of those around you. Social behavior is real behavior that allows a person to decide for himself in any role. Social expectations are the attitude of those around you towards this person. If someone makes a decision in this situation, it is as if those around them are "tied" to it. As students progress into high school, they not only become more aware of their social status, but also often seek to change their beliefs. Granted, social expectations are a barrier will give. Spending time 'smir' as social expectations are stable it will be difficult for the student to change the situation, the help of an educator is needed here. Since man is a social being, he has the ability to understand himself.[4. Only in social life, in all kinds of relationships with other people, does a person realize that he is "I" knowledge arises and develops. A person's self-awareness includes who he or she is as an individual, his or her past and future, his or her rights and duties,

and finally his or her own strengths and weaknesses. the force that influences is the growth and change of social factors, or in other words, the productive forces of society as well as the relations of production. In addition, another powerful factor influencing the composition of the human personality is man-made is that your experience is passed on to children through the means of upbringing.] The role of the external, social environment and upbringing in the mental development of a person and in the formation of personal qualities is of paramount importance. However, the composition of the human personality, as mentioned above, depends not only on these two factors, but also on a third factor. This factor is hereditary, some anatomical and biological is the effect of your character. Humans are inherited some anatomical and biological features. For example, body composition, hair and eye color, voice, speech patterns, and certain movements can be innate. However, it should never be forgotten that a person is never inherited the qualities that are related to his mental qualities, that is, his mental aspects. Finally, in rare cases, certain skills, such as music and math, can be inherited. There must be certain conditions for such opportunities to be realized.

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